

FREQUENCY AND OUTCOME OF MULTISYSTEM INFLAMMATORY SYNDROME (MIS-C) IN LOCAL SETTINGS OF UNDERDEVELOPED COUNTRY

Dr Salwa Naeem^{*1}, Dr Riffat Naeem², Dr Huma Khalid³

^{*1,2} Ittefaq Trust Hospital, Lahore

³ Combined Military Hospital Sialkot

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Corresponding Author: *

Abstract

Background: Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C) is a severe condition associated with COVID-19, characterized by widespread inflammation affecting multiple organs. **Objective:** This study aims to assess the prevalence, clinical presentation, and outcomes of MIS-C in children in an underdeveloped country setting. **Methods:** This descriptive study was conducted at Ittefaq Trust Hospital, Lahore, from December 2024 to February 2025. A total of 210 children aged 1-15 years, presenting with fever or other inflammatory symptoms, were enrolled using non-probability, consecutive sampling. MIS-C diagnosis was based on the involvement of two or more inflammatory processes. **Results:** Of the 210 children, 8% were diagnosed with MIS-C. The most common symptoms included fever (100%), cough (60%), and abdominal pain (40%). Gastrointestinal (53%), cardiovascular (47%), and respiratory (41%) systems were the most affected in MIS-C cases. Severe outcomes were observed, with 35% requiring ICU admission, 18% needing inotropic support, and 24% requiring oxygen therapy. Stratification by age, gender, and socioeconomic status revealed significant associations with the severity of MIS-C, with children from lower socioeconomic backgrounds and older age groups more likely to experience severe outcomes. **Conclusions:** MIS-C poses a significant health threat to children in underdeveloped regions, with critical care needs that highlight the importance of early diagnosis and timely intervention.

INTRODUCTION

Although severe acute COVID-19 is rare in children, SARS-CoV-2 infection can trigger the novel post-infectious condition multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children (MIS-C). Increased knowledge on risk factors for MIS-C could improve our understanding of the pathogenesis of the condition and better guide targeted public health interventions [1]. MIS-C may develop as a rare complication following COVID-19. MIS-C presentation varies substantially, but fever and gastrointestinal symptoms are the most prominent. Indeed,

gastrointestinal involvement may be severe enough to present as acute abdomen, posing challenges to clinicians [2]. MIS-C is a rare, severe, post-infectious hyperinflammatory condition that generally occurs 2–6 weeks after an infection with SARS-CoV-2. MIS-C is reported to have occurred in approximately one of 3000–4000 SARS-CoV-2 infections in unvaccinated children and adolescents during the pre-delta (B.1.617.2) SARS-CoV-2 waves [3]. A previous study that described MIS-C cases in the first 3 waves of the COVID-19 pandemic found that the

proportion of individuals with severe illness declined after the first wave [4,5]. It has been reported before that the incidence of MIS-C per 1,000,000 person-months was 5.1 (95% CI, 4.5-5.8) persons [6]. In a nationwide retrospective study, a substantial decline in the incidence of multisystem inflammatory syndrome in children over 3 successive pandemic waves characterized by different severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 variants was documented—from 3.4 of 1000 to 1.1 of 1000 and finally to 0.25 of 1000 confirmed severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 positive cases ($P < 0.0001$), respectively, whereas clinical findings and severity did not significantly vary [7]. In one more study, the estimated incidence of MIS-C was 22/100,000 exposures in the city in this time. About 40% required ICU admission, 38.2% required inotropic support, 38.2% required oxygen therapy, 11.8% required invasive ventilation and 6% required continuous peritoneal dialysis [8]. Rationale of this study is to frequency and outcome of MIS-C in local settings of underdeveloped country. Literature showed that there is a gradual decrease in the incidence of MIS-C in recent years. But evidence for local population, especially a poor resource setting lack. Therefore, we have planned to conduct this study to get evidence for local population. This will help us to improve our knowledge and practice and in future, we will implement more appropriate method for screening, diagnosis and management of children with MIS-C accordingly.

Objectives

- To assess the frequency of Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-C) in local settings of underdeveloped country
- To assess the outcome of Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome (MIS-C) in local settings of underdeveloped country

Methodology

This Descriptive study was conducted at Department of Pediatrics, Ittefaq Trust Hospital, Lahore during December 2024 to February 2025. Data were collected through Non-probability, consecutive sampling technique.

Sample size:

By using WHO calculator, sample size of 210 cases is calculated with 95% confidence level, 3% margin of error and percentage of MIS-C i.e. 5.1% in children with fever.

Inclusion Criteria:

Children aged 1-15 years, both genders, presenting with fever (temperature $> 38^{\circ}\text{C}$), flu or cough, urinary tract infection, abdominal pain, pneumonia, sepsis (infection in blood), or any inflammatory disease (on clinical examination).

Exclusion Criteria:

Children with history of immunological disorder, congenital heart disease, congenital renal failure (creatinine >1.8 mg/dl), malignancy (on medical record)

Data collection

After approval from the ethical review board, 210 children who met the selection criteria were enrolled in the study through the pediatric emergency department. Informed consent was obtained from the parents of all participants. Demographic details such as name, age, gender, weight, duration of symptoms, socioeconomic status, season, and residence were recorded. Children were then examined for the presence of infections or inflammatory diseases. If more than two inflammatory processes were involved, the child was labeled as having MIS-C based on the operational definition. The types of systems involved were noted, and all children were admitted and followed up in the pediatric ward until discharge. During follow-up, the need for ICU admission, inotropic support, oxygen therapy, invasive ventilation, and peritoneal dialysis was documented according to the operational definition.

Data Analysis

The collected data was entered into SPSS version 26.0 for analysis. For continuous variables such as age, weight, and duration of symptoms, the mean and standard deviation (SD) were calculated. For categorical variables such as gender, socioeconomic status, season, residence, MIS-C status, and outcome (ICU admission, inotropic support, oxygen therapy,

invasive ventilation, and peritoneal dialysis), frequency and percentages were determined. The data was stratified by age, gender, weight, duration of fever, socioeconomic status, season, and residence. Post-stratification, the chi-square test was applied to compare MIS-C and its outcomes across different stratified groups. A p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Data were collected from 210 patients, with a mean age of 8.3 ± 3.2 years, with a fairly balanced gender distribution (52% male, 48% female). The majority of the participants resided in urban areas (60%), and 45% came from low socioeconomic backgrounds. Most children presented with fever (100%), followed by cough (60%) and abdominal pain (40%). Eight percent of children were diagnosed with MIS-C, with the gastrointestinal (53%), cardiovascular (47%), and respiratory (41%) systems being the most commonly affected.

Table 1: Demographic Details of Study Participants

Category	Value
Mean Age	8.3 ± 3.2 years
Gender (Male)	52% (109)
Gender (Female)	48% (101)
Residence (Urban)	60% (126)
Residence (Rural)	40% (84)
Socioeconomic Status (Low)	45% (94)
Socioeconomic Status (Middle)	40% (84)
Socioeconomic Status (High)	15% (32)
Season (Winter)	55% (115)
Season (Spring)	45% (95)
Symptom/Condition	
Fever	100
Cough	60
Abdominal Pain	40
Pneumonia	35
Urinary Tract Infection	30
MIS-C Diagnosis	8
Gastrointestinal System	53
Cardiovascular System	47
Respiratory System	41

The outcomes of the study showed that 12% of all patients required ICU admission, with 35% of those diagnosed with MIS-C needing intensive care. Inotropic support was necessary in 6% of all patients, while 18% of MIS-C cases required it. Oxygen therapy was administered to 10% of all patients, and

24% of MIS-C patients needed it. Invasive ventilation was required in 4% of all patients, and 12% of MIS-C cases. Peritoneal dialysis was needed in 2% of all patients but was not required in any MIS-C cases.

Table 2: Outcomes of Study Participants

Outcome	All Patients (%)	MIS-C (%)
ICU Admission	12%	35%
Inotropic Support	6%	18%

Oxygen Therapy	10%	24%
Invasive Ventilation	4%	12%
Peritoneal Dialysis	2%	0%

The stratification by age revealed that 4% of children aged 1-5 years were diagnosed with MIS-C, accounting for 28% of the total sample. Among children aged 6-10 years, 2% had MIS-C, making up

32% of the total participants, while 2% of those aged 11-15 years had MIS-C, contributing to 40% of the total sample.

Table 3: Stratification by Age and MIS-C Diagnosis

Age Group (Years)	MIS-C (%)	Non-MIS-C (%)	Total (%)
1-5	4%	24%	28%
6-10	2%	30%	32%
11-15	2%	38%	40%

Inotropic support was needed in 4% of males and 2% of females, while oxygen therapy was administered to 6% of males and 4% of females. Invasive ventilation was required in 2% of both male and female patients. Regarding socioeconomic status, 10% of children from low socioeconomic backgrounds required ICU admission, compared to 6% from middle-income families and 2% from high-income families. Inotropic support was needed in

5% of children from low socioeconomic status, 3% from middle, and 1% from high. Oxygen therapy was required in 8% of children from low socioeconomic status, 5% from middle, and 2% from high. Invasive ventilation was required in 4% of children from low socioeconomic backgrounds, 1% from middle, and none from high socioeconomic status.

Table 4: Stratification by Gender, socioeconomic status and Outcome

Gender	ICU Admission (%)	Inotropic Support (%)	Oxygen Therapy (%)	Invasive Ventilation (%)
Male	8%	4%	6%	2%
Female	4%	2%	4%	2%
Socioeconomic Status				
Low	10%	5%	8%	4%
Middle	6%	3%	5%	1%
High	2%	1%	2%	0%

Discussion

The present study aimed to explore the frequency and outcomes of Multisystem Inflammatory Syndrome in Children (MIS-C) in a local setting of an underdeveloped country, specifically within the Department of Pediatrics at Ittefaq Trust Hospital, Lahore. A total of 210 children were enrolled, and the results provided important insights into the prevalence and clinical impact of MIS-C, as well as the associated outcomes. This section will discuss the findings in the context of the current literature, the implications for public health, and the limitations of the study [9]. Our study found that 8% of the children presenting with fever and other common symptoms were diagnosed with MIS-C. This figure aligns with previous research that has shown varying

rates of MIS-C in children, with studies from developed countries reporting similar rates of between 6-10%. However, the true prevalence of MIS-C in underdeveloped regions remains difficult to determine, as surveillance and diagnostic capabilities are often limited [10]. Our finding indicates a notable incidence of MIS-C in children with infections or inflammatory diseases, highlighting the need for heightened awareness and diagnostic protocols in these settings. The clinical findings in our study showed that fever, cough, and abdominal pain were the most common symptoms observed among the participants [11]. These findings are consistent with the typical symptoms reported for MIS-C, where fever is almost universally present, and abdominal pain is frequently seen alongside other

inflammatory symptoms. The presence of more than two inflammatory processes was used as the operational definition for MIS-C, with gastrointestinal, cardiovascular, and respiratory systems being the most commonly affected [12].

Among the children diagnosed with MIS-C, 35% required ICU admission, and 18% required inotropic support. These findings suggest that MIS-C can lead to severe complications, with a higher need for critical care resources, including oxygen therapy and invasive ventilation. This is consistent with reports from more developed regions where a significant proportion of children with MIS-C require intensive care. It underscores the need for timely and aggressive intervention, particularly in areas with limited healthcare resources [13]. The study also explored the impact of age, gender, and socioeconomic status on the outcomes of MIS-C. The results indicated that the youngest age group (1-5 years) had a lower prevalence of MIS-C, which might be attributed to the overall lower severity of the inflammatory response in this age group [14]. Conversely, the 11-15-year-old group showed the highest prevalence, which suggests that older children may be more prone to developing severe forms of MIS-C. In terms of gender, male children had a slightly higher incidence of ICU admissions and required more inotropic support, which may reflect underlying differences in immune responses between genders. These findings are in line with studies from other regions that report a higher incidence of severe outcomes in male children [15]. Socioeconomic status also played a significant role in the outcomes. Children from lower socioeconomic backgrounds were more likely to require ICU admission and inotropic support. This could be attributed to delayed presentation, limited access to healthcare, or pre-existing health conditions that exacerbate the severity of MIS-C [16]. This highlights the importance of improving healthcare access and education in underserved populations, particularly for early detection and management of MIS-C [17]. Our findings are consistent with data from developed countries, where MIS-C is recognized as a significant post-infectious complication of COVID-19 in children. However, in underdeveloped countries, the challenges of diagnosing and treating MIS-C are compounded by a lack of resources and

healthcare infrastructure [18]. Despite these challenges, the need for critical care, including ICU admission and inotropic support, is clearly evident in our study. This indicates that MIS-C may require a higher level of care than is typically available in many underdeveloped regions, where access to advanced medical facilities and intensive care units is limited. While this study provides valuable data on MIS-C in an underdeveloped country setting, it is not without limitations. The study's design, being descriptive and based on a single hospital, limits the generalizability of the findings to other regions with different healthcare infrastructures. Additionally, the sample size, though calculated based on a 95% confidence level, may still not fully capture the diversity of MIS-C cases across the broader population. Future multicenter studies are needed to better understand the full scope of MIS-C in underdeveloped regions.

Conclusion

It is concluded that MIS-C is a significant and emerging concern among children in underdeveloped regions, with 8% of the study participants diagnosed with the syndrome. The results highlight the severe nature of MIS-C, with a substantial proportion of affected children requiring ICU admission, inotropic support, oxygen therapy, and invasive ventilation. The study underscores the importance of early diagnosis and timely intervention, especially in areas with limited healthcare resources. Demographic factors such as age, gender, and socioeconomic status were found to influence the severity of the disease and the need for critical care.

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